

Gravitons make all matter

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Received: 11 of September 2026

Accepted: 20 of December 2026

In this work, we further develop the *faster than light (FTL) field* model^[1a,1b,1c], to show how all matter is derived of gravitons; (gravitons are the photons' equivalent of the faster than light field). In the process of creating quarks and electrons from gravitons at extreme conditions, gravitons' derivatives are formed and squeezed together. The combined particle of these processes is either an electron or a quark. Gravitons are also responsible for dark energy and dark matter signals, making gravitons the source of all energy in our real space.

This model also explaining the source of the electron's charge (and quarks' charge): it is the electrical lobes of the gravitons that made it. Electrons and up and down quarks and photons are real entities, yet most other particles in the standard model are highly structured graviton layers, perhaps in combination with the real entities, that are identified as unique particles, in various experiments. The model further explaining that forces affect from a distance through FTL gravitons' layering; the FTL layers formation was described in previous works and is further developed here, showing that gravity and electromagnetism have the same basic gravitons' layering structure, yet different gravitons' orientation and transients within. The strong force among quarks is simply a highly structured and very dense gravitons' layers. So the FTL field model replaces all 17 fields that were suggested during the years in quantum field theory to describe reality.

This model suggesting that anti matter does not cause anti gravity effects; as with photons, gravity is symmetric, in this respect. And different universes in the multiverse might have the opposite definition for anti matter.

My theory is simple to verify: it is the only theory that is based on FTL signals and field; so proving that such signals exist, is proving the theory. Ways to perform such experiments and interpretation of recent and older experimental results within the prism of my theory are presented.

Valuable Phrases; gravity; *theory of everything*; faster than light phenomenon; anti gravity technology;

PACS; 04.00.00; 04.60.-m; 04.60.Cf; 47.35.Bb; 95.85.Sz

1. Introduction.

What is the source of the charge of an electron? This question is answered in this work, within the *faster than light field* model, developed in previous works [1a,1b,1c], and further polished here. The answer is gravitons. The process to form electrons from gravitons is explained fully within the faster than light (FTL) field model, in the part dealing with the way matter is created at the interface of the real space and the faster than light field, in extreme conditions. Electrons, and quarks are created in extreme gravity conditions, in the interface of the two spaces; there, gravitons are squeezed into a spiral whose central point or region is the connection between the spaces, and at this region, matter is created and emerges into the real space. **Figure 1a** illustrates the interface of these

two spaces, where Fig.2 in Section 2 showing the how quarks and electrons are composed from squeezed gravitons' transients.

The *faster than light field* model is not an equation as the Schrödinger equation. It is a model. It clearly has equations of motion for dynamics, as shown in simulations [1a, 1c], yet the scaling law analyses¹ of this model are the tool to derive results. And the number of powerful results that are derived in these analyses is very large, about 100 results (including this work) are derived from this model, most were not known before, or around debated subjects, in various relevant areas in physics as quantum mechanics, elementary particle physics, and cosmology, and in relevant applications.

In the research to develop a microscopic model for gravity and the *theory of everything*², we concluded that gravity is a process of wave creation around matter, and the description is complete with a theory that can explain what and where the illusive graviton particles are [4]. This task was accomplished with the derivation of the *faster than light field* model, also termed the *imaginary mass field*, presented in the trilogy [1a,1b,1c]. We developed there the model saying that there is a field, complementary to ours, whose signals are faster than light (FTL). The particles of that field emit gravitons spontaneously and all the time, for not to freeze to the speed of light. Gravitons are the photons' equivalent of that field. In principle, gravitons are not detected in our real space with regular measurement tools of our time, yet it is probably possible to infer gravitons from various specific experiments [1c]. Gravitons are spin 2, and have double the lobes of photons, see Fig. 1b. Gravitons' properties are such that cause these particles to circle every electro and magnetic fluctuation in the real space. Once a structure of gravitons form a stationary wave, it affects real space as it is not longer faster than light. These structures form the gravity force [1a], yet also all fundamental microscopic forces [1b] and have many interesting consequences on our real space processes and occurrences [1c], from big bangs to the structure of Atoms.

Figure 1. A. The Illustration of the two spaces at big bang conditions. B. The Illustrational of the graviton. It has double the lobes of the photon, and spin 2 properties.

Our goal in this work is first to explain what is the difference between gravity and electromagnetism, within this model of the faster than light field, mechanistic wise. After all, both are very similar in scaling laws [1a, 1b] and scale the same with the distance r , r^{-2} , and in both, the same layering of graviton made waves exists (these waves deliver or propagate the force signal)

1 The scaling laws are the main tool in analyzing the model, and this including the following generalizations: simulations of simplifier versions of the dynamics, numerical value analysis, and consistency checks.
2 The *theory of everything* is the most looked for theory in physics of our time, and should connect Einstein spacetime, the Higgs field, and quantum mechanics. Various known theoretical attempts include, string theory [2] and quantum gravity [3]

[1b]. In this work, we show that the orientation property and transient type, of gravitons in the graviton made wave, is different among gravity and electromagnetism, and this causes the differences. This analysis is also valid to the strong force and the weak force, with adjustments.

We also deal with the source of the charge property of the electron; this is explained through the process of creating matter from squeezed gravitons. The source of the electric charge of the electron is the negative lobes of the squeezed gravitons. And so on, for quarks. Photons are the language of real matter and are not created from squeezed gravitons, in principle, although are probably emitted during gravitons' passing through the spaces, in big bang conditions, for example.

There are various interesting results from these recent derivations; such that gravitons are the source of all matter and energies in our real space, and the source for all forces, and signals³. Yet also, anti matter does not cause anti gravity effects, as assumed in various documents [5]. And indeed, there are universes in the multiverse that our anti matter is the matter there⁴. Among the most valuable results in this work is the identification of the basic elementary particles and those that are not particle at all, just highly structured gravitons layers, or composite entities; for example, the Higgs boson is not a particle at all, it is a highly structured graviton made waves' structures around relativistic particles. The top ten results in this work are summarized in table 1.

Table 1: The ten major results of this work

1	Big bang	Squeezed Gravitons and possibly photons are accumulated before the explosion type event happens;
2	Big bang	Squeezed Gravitons' transients make all matter: quarks and electrons are created. Then atoms.
3	Electron properties	The electron charge property is derived from the negative lobes of the squeezed gravitons' transients that make it.
4	Elementary particles physics	The real entities are: electrons, up and down quarks, photons. And neutrinos. All other particles in the standard model are not real particles. These are highly structured gravitons' layers, or in combination with the real entities.
5	Strong force	Gluons are not particles. These entities are highly structured and very dense gravitons' layers, made of a mixture of gravitons' transients, identified as particles in various experiments.
6	Higgs field boson	Higgs boson is not a particle. It is highly structured and dense gravitons' layers that are accumulated around relativistic particles. All gravitons in these layers are identical, for the "Higgs boson" case.
7	Weak & strong force processes;	In the nucleus, it is possible for FTL gravitons, to move into the within the c space. Yet most of the processes within the proton, for example, are related to transients of FTL gravitons' layers.
8	Gravity and Electromagnetism	In both cases, the graviton layers make the force; yet with different gravitons' transients within. And different densities. These differences cause the charge property propagation with distance, for example, of the electromagnetic force.
9	Gravity and antimatter	Antimatter does not cause anti gravity effects; gravity is symmetric in this respect, as photons.
10	Antimatter-matter-cosmology	Different universes in the multiverse have opposite definition for antimatter. Adjacent such universes might annihilate each other during the time

3 Excluding the photons emitted during gravitons' crossing of the spaces, most photons are not created from gravitons. Yet, through conservation laws in the real space, photons' energies are also derived of gravitons.

4 In the Nobel ceremony speech [6], Dirac talked about these issues, and claimed that different star systems might have opposite matter and anti matter definitions. Here, we claim that different universes in the multiverse will have the opposite definition of matter and antimatter.

(continued) Table 1. This table summaries just the main ten results in this work, spanning various areas in physics; from the big bang, to elementary particle identification, and antimatter cosmology.

On the structure of this document: on section 2, the creation of matter at the interface of the two spaces at extreme conditions is further developed. All matter structures are derived and spelled out. In Section 3, we deal with the way forces affect from a distance through the formation of FTL gravitons' layers. This also showing, for example, the difference between electromagnetism and gravity, with respect to properties of the FTL gravitons' in the layers. And in section 4, we conclude, and present various more interesting results, about the identification of the elementary particles within the FTL field model, about antimatter behaviors, and more.

Section 2: Matter emergence in big bang conditions; Gravitons make all matter.

Up and down quarks and electrons are formed from squeezed gravitons transients, that moved in our space from the FTL space, at big bang conditions. The basic process was developed in [1b]. This section further deals with that process down to the last detail.

The initial process for a big bang is the creation of dark matter signals from FTL gravitons waves, or sieves in that case, in a form of spiral; See Fig. 1A. During the time, more and more waves arrive to the confocal focus area of the spiral, that is changed into a symmetric shape. Gravitons are squeezed there. And also might form gravitons' transients, having just 3 electric lobes, for example. All these squeezed gravitons' constructs change their velocity to a fraction below c , from a fraction above c , and emerge in the real space, at the confocal area:

Equation 1 is a possibility for such a process; the process of the gravitons' crossing of the spaces in big bang conditions. The photons in Eq. (1) might have extreme energies, and are not related directly to the nowadays cosmic radiation, the microwave background radiation.

During the time, the radius of the cloud of real entities increases a lot, to a point where it stretches the faster than light field particles' density, to allow electrons and quarks to be created. Then atoms. And further stretching of the faster than light field particles' density, will create the level that will cause an explosion like process to occur, stretching in a sense space itself, in a split second, with all the particles that were created there during the time. The above is the FTL field model dynamics in big bang conditions. Further information in [1a].

In this work we derive the process of the creation of matter from the gravitons; what is created and how. The analysis show that up and down quarks and electrons are real entities. Muons and tau particles are constructs of real electrons and structured FTL layers of symmetric gravitons' layers. The other four quarks are hybrids of real quarks and structured FTL gravitons' layers. All are created form similar constructs that differ just in a type of gravitons' transients that make them.

For electrons, the gravitons' transients that are squeezed together to form the electron are a 3 leg electrical variant of the symmetric graviton. The transient has the two negatively charged lobes and just one positively charged lobe. See Fig. 2A. These are arranged in up and down orientation; See Fig. 2A. The magnetic lobes are all there. The positron variant has the complementary lobes; see Fig. 2D.

For up and down quarks, two types of graviton transients are squeezed together to form the base subunit of each, where these subunits are different. For up quark: a 3 leg electrical variant of the symmetric graviton and a symmetric graviton. The transient has the two positively charged lobes and just one negatively charged lobe. See Fig. 2B. In a basic subunit of the up quark, there are 3 gravitons: two transients having 3 electric legs, and one symmetric graviton. See Fig. 2B. The magnetic lobes are all there. The quark is composed of the repetitive up quark subunit. These are arranged in a up and down orientation; See Fig. 2B. The anti up quark variant has the complementary lobes; see Fig. 2E. For the down quark: similar to the up quark transient, just replace the graviton transient with a 3 electric leg graviton that is negatively charged. Yet the base subunit has two symmetric gravitons and just one transient. See Fig. 2C. The antimatter down quark has a transient with the opposite lobe composition to that of the matter down quark; is shown in Fig. 2F.

Fig 2. In all figures, all the four graviton’s magnetic lobes are there (not shown for making the sketches simpler to view). In all figures, the gravitons and the transients that are shown exist in the *c* space. **A.** The electron is composed from a repeated base subunit that has just three electric lobes, two negative and one positive. These transients are packed together in a compact up down configuration. **B.** The up quark subunit is composed of two graviton transients, with 3 legs, and one symmetric graviton, packed together is a tight configuration. The transients are identical, with two positive lobes and one negative lobe. **C.** The down quark: its subunit is composed of two symmetric gravitons and one transient, packed together in a tight configuration. The transient has 3 lobes, two negative and one positive. **D.** the positron. The same as the electron, yet the transient graviton has two positive lobes and one negative lobe. **E.** Anti up quark. The same as the up quark, yet the identical transients in the base subunits have two negative lobes and one positive lobe, each. **F.** Down anti quark. The same as the down quark, yet the transient in the base subunit has two positive lobes and one negative lobe.

The dynamics of the creation of these particles involve a gradual decrease in the density of the FTL gravitons layers; producing electron/positron subunits and quark/antiquark subunits. Then, Creating all sorts of seas of transients that do not annihilate each other. Then, electrons and quarks triplets are

formed, to create stable structures, and so on. The symmetry in producing positron and electron is clear and obvious. Compare Fig. 2A and 2D. Yet also, the positron base subunit appears in the up quark base subunit, together with a symmetric graviton. All these transients always are circled by FTL gravitons, that make the strong force, and cause structures to exist and not to annihilate each other. All known results are reproducible within this model. For example, it is clear that up quark, Fig 2B, and down anti quark, Fig 2F, will create an electron, perhaps with additional gravitons' layers, what is known as a muon. More on muons in section 4. Yet further more: Fig 2 suggests that two up quarks for example, should not annihilate each other, otherwise a positron should not exist. And so, for many other known examples. Everything fits within this FTL field model, on the matter of "how quarks and electrons are formed".

Section 3: Differences in the layering of gravitons in the various forces;

In this section, we deal with and develop further the FTL gravitons' layering around real matter, the source of all fundamental forces, based on the FTL field model; these layers form all fundamental forces showing the same source to all forces. The identification shows various interesting results, such that the Higgs boson is not a particle at all. It is a highly structured and dense FTL gravitons' layering, occurring around relativistic particles, perhaps also causing gravitons to appear in the c space.

The FTL layers for gravity are shown in Fig. 3A; shown are just the electrical lobes, as all four magnetic lobes (per graviton) are there, and span the xy plane (which is always at right angles to the pulling direction), making the fabric of the force in the xy plane. In gravity, the graviton has just a particular electric lobe type, either the plus lobes or the minus lobes, for these particles to circle matter. During the time, both lobes' types may appear, yet the important issue is that the lobes' type ordering changes in time, making gravity indifferent to charges and magnetic signals; see Fig. 3B.

For the electric force in electromagnetism, both the electric lobes' types are there⁵; see Fig. 3C. This force has the same layers' ordering in time, making possible for the layering to pull electric signals or to repel electric signals. It is clear that the ordering is a property that is simpler to have just around the real matter, and with the distance, the order of the layers might mix, making electromagnetism a short distance force, in comparison to gravity.

For the magnetic force in electromagnetism, both types of the magnetic lobes of the FTL graviton are clearly there, and both electric types. The force is obtained from a tilt of the magnetic lobes; for example, a up tilt for north lobes, and a down tilt for south lobes. See Fig. 3D. The tilt changes along a circumference of the layer, based on the situation in the direction of lobes in the real matter; see Fig. 3D. This is a unique property for the FTL layers, that is seen just for magnetism. It explains why magnetic monopoles are not seen in nature at all, although are not impossible. More on this in section 4.

For the strong force, the layers are highly dense, made of FTL gravitons, perhaps a mixture of transients; see Fig. 3E. The fact that the FTL transients might have asymmetry increases the force magnitude.

For the Higgs boson, the layers are of FTL symmetric gravitons, with orientation that mixes with time (much faster than c space timescales), yet various FTL gravitons might move to the c space,

⁵ Perhaps just during wave formation, there is a particular type just. Although this is not required, as the electric signal of the real matter can direct the formation of the FTL gravitons' layers.

based on the velocity of the relativistic particles, and the conditions, as the macroscopic density. The density of the FTL layers is very high around the real structure. See Fig. 3F.

For the weak force: there are several processes within the weak force. In most cases, a weak force process involving both FTL gravitons and gravitons that moved to the c space. The full discussion about the weak force is presented in section 4.

Fig 3. The way forces work from a distance, within the FTL field model. A. gravity. B. gravity layers' fluctuations. C. electromagnetism, the eclectic field. D. electromagnetism, the magnetic field. E. the strong force. F. Higgs layering

Section 4: Discussion and concluding comments

4.1. *A concise summary;* In this work, we showed how exactly the FTL field model generates all particles in our space, and all fundamental forces⁶. This section shows that the FTL field model has a unique characterization of the elementary particles, and other interesting results about antigravity and antimatter. The FTL field model replaces the 17 fields that were claimed, during the years, to

⁶ Although both topics appeared in the trilogy [1a, 1b, 1c], this work further developed these to a point that clarify various more unsolved matters in physics in various relevant areas.

exist; due to poor understanding of reality, there was an inflation in fields, from the Higgs field, to the quark field, the gluon field, etc, all these fields do not exist at all. What do exist is the FTL field.

4.2. About all particles in the standard model:

The *faster than light field* model has its own classification of particles; see Fig. 4. Such a classification, with all its accompanied explanations, is very important and can greatly advance in this field. Here, there are just 3 real entities with mass: electrons, up and down quarks. Where this in addition to the massless photons, and the FTL field gravitons. The other particles in the standard model are either highly structured and dense FTL graviton layers (that can have different gravitons' transients within), as Higgs boson and gluons, or the real entities surrounded by highly structured and dense FTL graviton layers, as muon and tau particles, and the other four quarks. Neutrinos in case exist are also possible in the FTL field model, as particles. Table 2 summaries these matters.

Fig. 4. The standard model classification of particles versus FTL field model classification.

4.2.1. A Muon or a tau particle: this particle is an electron that got fused with layers of symmetric FTL gravitons in mild conditions, conditions that are much weaker in density compare to big bang conditions. The gravitons' outer layers are much denser than standard gravitons' layers that occurring in gravity. Yet probably less dense than those in the strong or the weak interactions. The gravitons' transients in these layers are symmetric, as a muon or a tau particle has the same charge magnitude as an electron. The fact that these are symmetric graviton layers, cause the layers to dissipate in a split second, upon creation. See Fig. 5A.

An electron is not so dense compare to quarks, as it has the same repetitive subunit, unlike up and down quarks, that have symmetric gravitons immersed in the base subunit, in addition to other graviton transients, allowing tighter packing. Therefore, the additional outer layers in muon and tau might show higher densities than the electron itself. This means that the size of these particles, tau and muon, will look the same as electron, in current situation with nowadays measurement tools. The additional layers are much denser than the core, and this cause the instabilities, and the short half life of these particles, in particular, the tau particle. See Fig 5B.

4.2.2. The other quarks (charm, strange, top, bottom): The other 4 quarks are all similar in the sense that these are constructs of a real quark with highly structured FTL graviton layers around it, in the periphery. The heavier ones are very unstable; very similar to a tau particle and a muon, the heavier these hybrid particles are, the lower their stability is. See Fig 5C, 5D.

4.2.3. *The neutrinos*; These are particles with the same basic subunit of a symmetric c space graviton. We can depict a neutrino as a small ball made of the symmetric gravitons packed together. Their spin $\frac{1}{2}$ indicates on the connections among gravitons in the construct. The fact that these are so small, show what is the upper bound for a particle to exist in a stable state, without electrical and magnetic biases in its basic subunits. **See the illustration in Fig 5E.**

4.2.4. *Boson Higgs*; A highly dense structured gravitons layers around relativistic particles. Its properties of spherical symmetric, 0 charge and Spin 0, means: it has the same symmetric FTL graviton in its basic subunit. Heavy and short lived as in the case of composite electrons and composite quarks. The layers are in the periphery of the real matter, and there is all the mass, causing instabilities. The fact that the real particles are relativistic causes the FTL layers' density to further increase. The symmetry is referring to the spin of the whole layering structure, on the level of the envelope. **See Fig. 4F.**

4.2.5. *The gluons*; A highly dense, structured, FTL gravitons layers between quarks. Mixture of gravitons and gravitons' transients. Therefore spin 1, characterizing the level of the envelope of the structure. **See Fig. 4E.**

4.2.6. W^\pm and Z bosons; These are unique composite entities. These represent the gateway between the spaces, FTL and c space, in the everyday conditions of the quarks and Atom's nucleus, rather than the big bang conditions. These entities can be viewed as the accountant mass book, and also use the strong force made of FTL gravitons' layering among quarks, to act.

To define these bosons, we depict the beta decay process within the FTL field model, as follows: FTL gravitons are moved to the within c space and are included inside the up quark; during that process, various base subunits of the up quark are taken to make the electron base subunit; and on that, FTL gravitons' transients are moved to the c space and are accompanied the evolving electron structure. All these processes define the W^- boson, in addition to the FTL gravitons' layers of the transforming quark that were involved in the processes. **See Fig 5F.**

Figure 5. The composite entities. In all illustrations: the inner red and black circles represent vert dense FTL layers, and perhaps, gravitons' layering in c space. A. Muon; B. tau. C. top quark D. strange quark. E, neutrino F. W boson.

So in fact the weak force involves the strong force together with the electromagnetic force, yet here on the quark level. For beta decay: the strong force repulsion between the two adjacent up quarks, and the electromagnetic repulsion of the evolving electron and the up quark, form the repulsion weak force, to facilitate the beta decay process. For beta electron capture: electromagnetic attraction that increases as the electron spiral into the down quark. This causes the FTL gravitons' layers of the strong force to get squeezed more and more, transforming FTL gravitons into c space gravitons' transients, in the outer layers of the transforming down quark. The strong force repulsion between the two adjacent down quarks decreases. In both cases, beta decay and beta capture, the weak force is composed of the strong force (FTL gravitons' layers), the electromagnetic force variant, and FTL gravitons that move into the c space. The type of gravitons' transients that appear in the c space define the type of bosons that are involved in the process; either W^\pm boson or the Z boson.

Table 2.

Electron	Real entity	3 leg c space graviton's transient	
Up and down quarks	Real entity	Mixtures of symmetric and 3 leg c space graviton's transients	
photon	Real entity,	unique c space massless wave;	The language of real matter
neutrinos	Real entity	Symmetric c space graviton.	Define lower bound for matter to exist as a particle
Other 4 quarks	Composite entity	Up or down quark surrounded with FTL gravitons' layers.	
Muon and Tau	Composite entity	Electron surrounded with FTL gravitons' layers.	
Gluons	FTL structured gravitons' layers	Mixtures of FTL gravitons.	
Higgs boson	FTL structured gravitons' layers	Symmetric FTL graviton.	
W and Z bosons	Special composites	Mixtures of FTL gravitons and c space gravitons (within processes)	The gateway between the spaces

Table 2. The characterization of all the particles, of the FTL field model.

4.2.7. Miscellaneous. In this subsection, we deal with various relevant processes within the FTL field model that can further define or explain the definitions of particles in this model; what is a particle, and what is a force combined with FTL gravitons' layering, just. We also comment on various debated issues, as the existence of magnetic monopoles, neutrinos as a Majorana particle, antimatter and antigravity, etc.

4.2.7.1 The nuclear fusion is different than weak force processes, as the beta capture for example, and does not require FTL gravitons conversion to c space.

4.2.7.2. In the process of electron capture,

FTL gravitons are converted into the real space; this is required, as the up quark, the lighter quark, is transformed into the down quark.

Running title: We are made of graviton transients

4.2.7.3. The neutrinos are probably Majorana particles and are their own anti particle. This is a consequence of the FTL field model identification of the elementary particles, and their composition. Neutrinos are made of symmetric c space gravitons. A symmetric graviton is its own antimatter. See Fig. 5E.

4.2.7.4. Magnetic monopoles might exist. Manipulation on the graviton level is required to create such a material in the lab. In nature, it can occur just in case a swap of the graviton's magnetic and electric lobes happens. So a magnetic monopole is definable with the FTL field model; it is not an arbitrary construct. In supp info, we show various more illustrative figures relevant to this work, in particular, Fig.SI. 3 shows a monopole construct, within the FTL field model.

4.3. Anti gravity matters;

4.3.1. About antigravity for antimatter.

This subject appeared since the 1960s [5]. Yet based on my theory, antimatter will not cause antigravity effects. The mass is not negative at all. It is neutral. It does not matter if the electron's charge is negative or positive, with respect of gravity. At least, as far as we can measure, the gravitons' lobes orientation in gravity layers are symmetric. In case there is an effect, as the outer layer of all real matter in Atoms is negatively charged, and a tiny orientation shift might occur, antimatter and matter will feel the slightest attraction also due to gravity, and not any repulsion.

4.3.2. About anti gravity effects; in applications:

This issue appeared in the trilogy [1a,1b,1c]. We showed that electromagnetic signal can affect the gravity force; The signal frequency will have the effect, and so the power of the electrical signal, its voltage and amperage. Radiant signals are required. And also Magnetic signals. There are anti gravity effects that pierce the Earth gravity, and anti gravity to change the density of the faster than light field's particles. This analysis that appeared in [1] is further supported in this work, see Fig. 3.

4.4. Anti matter within the FTL field model.

4.4.1. About anti matter definition in a particular universe

Each universe might have its own definition for what matter is. Photons are the same and so is the force of gravity; both are symmetric, as can be seen from Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

4.4.2. *The fate of the expansion process and of opposite matter adjacent universes;*

The expansion process might cause all matter to disappear or to wander to a different universe, yet there might be a case when the expansion process reaches a steady state against gravitational forces within. In case adjacent universes are opposite in their matter configuration, annihilation will take place in the first scenario. Whether a complete annihilation or a partial one takes place depending on various parameters or processes and their consequences on the expansion process in each universe.

4.5. *How to prove this "theory of everything"? With the identification of FTL signals;*

Indeed, my FTL theory can explain numerous unsolved mysteries in physics, and is based on mathematical formulations and scaling laws and simulations, where all these analyses can be performed and tested independently. Yet also, this theory forming a tool to tackle many other matters in relevant areas, including the development of applications; both can be tested independently to form another pillar of such proofs. Nevertheless one can ask: how can we verify

this theory in experiments? The answer: My theory is unique in utilizing FTL signals; and proving that such exist, is to prove this theory.

Since Einstein's works, it was a taboo: FTL signals do not exist; although the paradox is that the Lorentz scaling factor shows exactly where to look for such signals, and how to develop a theory with such signals. During the years, various papers dealt with theoretical particles that are faster than light, yet not any theory was built based on FTL signals, in particular, such that explains everything in physics, connecting gravity and electromagnetism and the strong force, explaining galaxies yet also the origin of matter, and the electron's composition, etc.

There are, today, various results that already show and indicate that FTL signals exist. These are not quantum entanglement arguments, and not signals that do not carry energy nor information. These FTL signals are not photons that move with a different c value, although my theory can show that the value of c can change when the density of the FTL field's particles changes, in for example black holes (where c goes to zero) or between galaxies (where c there might slightly increase). In principle, among the ways to show FTL signals include:

1. Radiant energy quenching of gravity: interactions of gravity waves with radiant energy that is emitted from a Tesla tower [REF]. We talked about this in a whole section in the previous paper [1c], here we emphasize that as stemming from Tesla patents from 1905 [ref], it is possible to show that gravity is faster than light in an apparatus with multiple receivers and a powerful Tesla coil transmitter, and that we plan to perform such experiments that were not performed since 1905.
2. CERN type experiments of particles accelerator: although not bound to FTL signals, CERN type experiments show a lot of discrepancies with the standard model, in particular in recent years with improving measurements' accuracy [REF]. Every time that another paper claiming that "another particle is required to explain the measurements", is another support to my claims that the standard theory of particles contains particles that are not real particles, and the 17 fields of the standard model do not exist at all; the real explanation to these measurements is the FTL field, forces, and properties. These CERN type measurements capture gravitons signatures, and not Higgs bosons or signals from 17 fields, among other obsolete quantities.
3. Results about the expansion of the universe: my theory is the only theory that explaining that space is not "an inflating ballon in a rate faster than light" as claimed by spacetime advocates that take Einstein spacetime theory at face value, which indeed is an argument that does not make much sense; it is the FTL field particles interacting with gravitational signals causing such effects with an upper bound speed of c^3 . So rather than space itself, space has FTL particles inside and all around, that cause these inflating FTL properties.
4. Anti gravity device: although not bound to FTL signals, relating gravity and electromagnetic signals, in for example an anti gravity device, can experimentally verify my FTL theory of everything⁷. Since my theory suggests that gravity has FTL signals, this discussion is relevant here, and clearly relevant to answering the question: how to verify my FTL theory of everything. Examples include:
 - 4.1. Tesla Tower and Earthquakes; We talked about this process in a recent publication [REF], yet it also mentioned here in a concise version as it is related to the current

⁷ There might be other theories claiming on connecting gravity and electromagnetism yet these are not as robust as my FTL theory; the connection should be made through the FTL field, otherwise leads to contradictions.

discussion. This system is a different version of the large Tesla coil system discussed above in 1, and is also related to proofing my FTL theory of everything: in a very powerful scale, it is claimed that a Tesla coil system, or a Tesla tower, can cause an earthquake [ref]. Clearly, this shows a connection between gravity or antigravity and electro magnetic signals. We plan to also study this process, to detect antigravity effects rather than earthquakes.

4.2. Searl effect levitation: as we indicated in a previous publication [REF], there are various systems and processes that were reported during the years and relate anti gravity effects with electro magnetic devices and processes, among the most famous is the Searl effect levitation, that might be related to the ionic wind phenomenon, yet other claims were also made.

4.3. Recent experiments in vacuum, and high voltage or high current, on a millimetric scale, show interesting motions of objects, in such conditions, relating possibility gravity and electromagnetism [REF].

4.6. *Various philosophical thoughts about the origin of existence, within the prism of my FTL theory;*

In this section, we philosophically discuss the origin of existence: whether god is required or the composite FTL-*c*-spaces can replace the need for a god creator to explain existence. The short answer is that there is a lot of room for interpretation, yet my theory is doing a much better work than other theories, as the big bang theory of the 20th century⁸, in explaining that existence does not require a god creator. The tension between the FTL and *c* spaces, is the origin of existence; although it does not require a god, it might represent a creator, or a creator's work.

About biological evolution: the origin of Molecules and Atoms is simpler to explain, yet evolution is also a mystery: based on evolution - a complex entity as a living cell might take much more time to evolve than claimed (10^{10} to 10^{100} more time than current estimations). My theory can explain this as influences between universes in the multiverse. Here, the multiverse is made of different universes that are not a quantum mechanical argument of each other; these are real universes, and each has an origin that occurred at a different time. As galaxies can roam between and among universes, bringing live matter to a younger universe, the appearance of living cells can happen much sooner than the slow estimation, in any particular universe.

References

1. a: O Flomenbom, *The Gravity Field: In the Origin of Matter and Almost Everywhere Else*, Reports in Advances of Physical Sciences, Reports in Advances of Physical Sciences Vol. 08, 2450003 (2024); b: The Imaginary Mass Field: In all Known Forces, Reports in Advances of Physical Sciences Vol. 09, 2550010 (2025); c: O Flomenbom, *The faster than light Field: further developments and results*, Reports in Advances of Physical Sciences, Reports in Advances of Physical Sciences Vol. 10, 2650002 (2026)
2. *string theory*
3. *quantum gravity*
4. a: O Flomenbom, *The Process of Gravity*, Reports in Advances of Physical Sciences, Vol. 06, 2250003 (2022); b: Quantum mechanics and gravity resonance together, Reports in Advances of Physical Sciences Vol. 08, 2471001 (2024);
5. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gravitational_interaction_of_antimatter

⁸ My theory has also a big bang at the origin of each universe, yet can answer what happened before and what is the source of matter, etc.

Running title: We are made of graviton transients

6. <https://www.nobelprize.org/uploads/2018/06/dirac-lecture.pdf>

Supplementary materials

Fig SI.1. this is a AI generated picture, of the standard model, for a proton, containing 3 quarks, gluons as springs, and a lot of transients in the background. The transients are just pairs of quarks, matter-antimatter.

Fig SI.2. The electron composition, according to the FTL field model. This is a AI generated picture, based on my definitions and sketches.

Fig SI.3. The magnetic monopole; North and South monopoles are shown. A monopole base subunit is a similar to that of the electron, yet here, the magnetic lobes are asymmetric, instead of the electric lobes. It might cause instabilities in the strength of the construct's surface. Including symmetric gravitons in the construct might increase the stability, yet might decrease the monopole signal.